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INNOVATIVE DESIGN OF PRODUCING LIGHT ON THE APPLICATION OF ELECTRICITY USING AN ANDROID DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

Home automation system has been around in the last decades and it offers a good solution to help preserve our natural resources and provides a variety of benefits such as comfort and quality of life. At the present time most home automation systems comprise of a microcontroller and a smartphone. A smart phone specifically an android or ios application is used to control home appliances using different type of wireless communication. An overview of emerging and current home automation systems in this paper is discussed. This system offers the overall design of an Android Based Home Automation System with low cost and wireless system that can lessen power consumption and automatically controlling electrical devices when aren't in use. This system is intended to offer and expands the ordinary living at home. The system implements wireless Bluetooth technology a short-range wireless communications technology to replace the cables connecting electronic devices, allowing a person to have a phone. Using this technology Bluetooth consumes low energy in comparison to other wireless communication. The system does provide more safety control in controlling light bulb with low voltage activating method. The key feature of this system is equipped with user-friendly mobile application equipped with user authentication with relatively low-cost design, interface and ease of installation.

Keywords: Arduino, Bluetooth, Home Automation, Smartphone

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INTRODUCTION

In the current times, we can see most of the individual clinging to their mobile phones all through the day. Day by day, the work and life of individual are increasingly busy and difficult. It is a test for the typical user to keep up with new improvements and sort through the growing offerings of products. What makes an environmentally friendly? Being environmentally friendly basically means reducing the effect on the environment as much as possible. In the present time, Automation is where things are being controlled automatically. The benefits of smart technology and home automation will continue to grow as technology continue to advance. The benefit of an automated system is lessening the human work, energy, time and mistakes due to human inattention. This system usually the basic tasks of turning on and off certain devices and beyond, either remotely or in close proximity. By applying this technology, we can save energy and delight in comfort. This paper presents the automated approach of controlling the devices in a domestic that would simplify the everyday jobs to use the traditional method of the switch. The research uses a combination of both hardware and software technologies that enable to control electrical devices that run on main power within a home using an android phone. N. Sriskanthan, F. Tan, A. Karande (Submitted for Publication , 2002) develop a home automation system based on Bluetooth wireless technology, that allows user to control and monitor different electrical device. Their project offers a great scope for further improvement.

R. Piyare & M. Tazil (Submitted for Publication, 2011) have implemented a low cost, flexible and wireless solution for home automation. It was found to be limited to 50 to 100 meters range depends on the applicability such as concreted building or in an open range. They were able to customize the application using Symbian OS design for the graphical user interface. However, its major drawback of Symbian OS is it provided a late response and the touch of Symbian use devices are not as smooth as compared to Android and ios. M. Muthukumaran, M. Kannusamy, M. Kanagaraj, A. Guruveswaran (Submitted for Publication, 2019) design and implement at low cost but flexible home automation system. Password protection is being used to permit only authorized users to use in which are needed to acquire pairing password. Though Bluetooth has certain limitations, such as a shorter range and lower bandwidth than Wi-Fi, it can make connectivity more reliable than other wireless alternatives between devices in your home. The system of Gaikwad and Kalshetty (Submitted for Publication, 2017) involves setting time that automatically shut off by thus is practicable since its cheap in terms of its cost and operation related to other device.

C. Felix and I. Jacob Raglend (Submitted for Publication, 2011) implemented flexible home

automation architecture using the potential of Zig-bee. ZigBee network offers itself as more efficient as it only uses low power requirements. However zigbee based communication is not secure from unauthorized people. It involves understanding of the system for the user to control zigbee compliant devices.

The purpose of this system implemented by J. Kumar et al. (Submitted for Publication, 2017) is to develop a home automation system using an Arduino board with Bluetooth being remotely controlled by any Android OS smart phone. The application program is tested on various Android mobile phones which are quite satisfactory and responses received from the community in general are encouraging. The android application software has been designed using Eclipse and Android Studio software. However this software mentioned requires a lot of memory for reliable work and powerful processor. The objectives of this project, implemented by Hishama et al. (Submitted for Publication, 2014) were achieved & successfully implemented this project. However, enhancements can be made to improve this project. Bluetooth connection between the android device and the controller is automatically recognized when the user begin to manipulate the mobile application. M. Bhojar (Submitted for Publication, 2014) gives basic idea of manipulating various home electrical devices and offer a security using Android devices. This paper is centered on Android and Arduino platform which both are Free Open Source Software. So, the overall implementation cost is cheap and affordable by a common person.

METHODOLOGY

How does it work?

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed system

Figure 1 is composed of five main parts to this system. An Android Device, a Bluetooth transceiver, an Arduino, Switching Relay and the Bulb. A Suitable app is designed to send serial data to the Bluetooth module which is HC-05. When a button is clicked on the mobile app, the Bluetooth module at the other end accepts the data and sends it to the Arduino through the Transmitter pin of the Bluetooth module. The program uploaded to the Arduino checks the received data and compares it. If the received data is 1on

(if(!strcmp(inStr,"1on"))), the LED turns ON. The LED turns OFF when the received data is 1off (if(!strcmp(inStr,"1off"))).

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the proposed system

Figure 2 displays the realistic pictures and how they are connected together. This diagram is simplified as it provides the means to easily identify the mechanisms of a system.

Hardware Connection

Guide for Bluetooth Module with Arduino

Connect the Bluetooth Module and its power sockets. Vcc to the Arduino 3.3 Volts and Ground to Arduino Ground. Connect the Tx (Transmitter Data) & Rx (receiver Data) of Bluetooth Module to the Arduino Rx and TX respectively.

Guide for Relay Module with Arduino and Bulb

The high-voltage side has two connectors, each with three sockets: normally closed (NC), normally open (NO) and common (COM), For Normally Open, the relay is always open, so the circuit is broken unless you send a signal from the Arduino to turn on the light bulb. For Normally Close, the current is flowing unless you send a signal to cut the current. For Switching Relay, Connect Vcc to the Arduino 5 Volts and Ground to Arduino Ground. The bulb is connected to the relay using a normally open configuration. The Arduino controls the relay through pin 2 which is connected to the relay Input.

Guide to power Arduino

Connect a 9V power adapter with the negative terminal connected to the Ground pin. Connect the positive terminal connected to the Voltage Input (Vin) pin. The Voltage Input port allows an input between 7 and 12 Volts. 3. Adding a switch to power adapter may use to manually turn off the system, when are not in use as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3. Actual design of proposed system

Figure 3 represents the working of the system. The system is applied using the Arduino Nano development board. The Power supply give them enough power to the microcontroller & related modules to operate correctly. This device has been automatically operated using Bluetooth module according to the command sent by the mobile to Arduino through the Bluetooth interface as shown in Figure 2. The microcontroller processes the data to switch the relay. Relay is basically an electrical device, usually consisting of an electromagnet, which is activated by a one circuit in which passing of current in to open or close another circuit. You could see of it as a switch that requires current to turn on or off. The number of I/O Channels is 1. Its switching capacity is available by 10A. The Control signal is in TTL level. The Max. Allowable voltage is 250VAC/110VDC. It has a LED indicator for Relay's Status

Figure 4. Upload a Sketch to an Arduino

Figure 4 shows how to upload the algorithm, copy the following code to your Arduino IDE and upload it to your Arduino board.

Arduino is an open-source platform for electronics that is easy-to-use hardware and software. It is widely use in several projects and applications. The Arduino software runs on different platform such as Mac, Windows and Linux. This platform is user friendly. Arduino code program using C language.

How to Upload a Sketch to an Arduino

Connect your microcontroller using the desired USB cable. Select Pick Tools → Board → Arduino Uno to find your board in the Arduino menu and select the desired serial port for your board 4. And click the upload button.

Figure 5. Installed application using MIT App Inventor

Figure 5 shows the installed application using MIT App Inventor (<https://appinventor.mit.edu/>). It allows newcomers to computer programming using Graphical User Interface (GUI) which allows users to drag and drop to create application that can run on android devices.

The results play a very important role in your paper. These serve as evidence of your method or idea you want propose. That there is an improvement or superiority in using your idea. In discussing your results, give due emphasis on the improvement or superiority of your method, but do not also forget its limitations. You may also discuss the results in comparison with other methods.

Figure 6. Login Screen

The above figure is the User Designer Interface and block design in creating a login screen for the security of the application. The default username is admin and password is 12345. When the user enter the correct username and password, it will go to screen 2 as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. Control Application

Figure 7 is the User Designer Interface & Block design for Screen 2. It consists of ListPicker wherein it displays a list of text for the use to choose among. A Bluetooth Client under Connectivity is added to in order to connect to other devices using this Bluetooth.

Figure 8. Building APK Application

An executable form (.apk) that can be shared and installed on a device, or in form (.aia) source code that can be import into App Inventor and revised.

How to Build APK Application

Build the application (.apk file) clicking the Build menu on the App Inventor toolbar as shown in Figure 8. Select Application and Save to my Computer. A pop-up box should alert you that your download has begun.

How to use Home Automation Application

1. Install & Open the application
2. Turn on the Bluetooth module by powering the Arduino.
3. Scan your smartphone for available device by pressing the ListPicker button
4. Pair your smartphone & select from the list the Bluetooth Module by entering default password 1234
5. After connecting successfully, press the ON button to turn the LED on and the OFF button to turn the LED off.
6. Disconnect the button to disconnect the Bluetooth module

Figure 9. Algorithm test

After uploading the algorithm, a test is required as shown in Figure 9. The android application contains the values that operate the system. In this application if button 1 is clicked, the electrical device will turn on. If this button 1 is clicked again, the electrical device will shut off

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Innovative Design of producing light on the application of electricity using an Android Device was a success. This System can have the ability of controlling the light bulb using this technology. The overall implementation was user friendly. In comparison with other wireless communication, the system consumes less energy, cheaper, thus it provided security and safety control in controlling the electrical device using smartphone installed with the suitable

application. The main control system implements wireless technology within its range from smartphone.

CONCLUSION

The objectives of this system was to design for converting electricity into light using Android Phone using Bluetooth wireless technology. The key feature of this system is equipped with user authentication. Though the overall of the project is completed successfully, this design can still be improved to enhance its capabilities and functionalities. The system needs a continuous power source to control the electrical device in case of power shortage. Importance of the method, and provide future research works.

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